

The effects of combining virtual laboratory and advanced technology research laboratory on university students' conceptual understanding of electron microscopy

Abstract

Development and evaluation of a teaching-learning activity in 4th year Forensic Physics course of Degree in Criminology was based on different combinations of a virtual laboratory and a research laboratory as teaching spaces. Students explored in detail the components and functioning of an electron microscope using both an online suite of education tools and an advanced scanning electron microscope (SEM). The aim of this study was to analyse the impact of all combinations of both activities on students' learning process, and to examine the effect on their interest towards the subject. A blend of research and virtual laboratories have a higher significant impact on students' achievements rather than each one separately, but the same is not true for student interest in scientific careers. These results confirm that the use of a research laboratory combined with a virtual one can have substantial benefits in improvement students' knowledge about abstract and complex concepts.

Keywords: electron microscopy; virtual laboratory; criminology; scientific career; students' interest; forensic physics

1. Introduction

The European Higher Education Area (EHEA) has conceptually reformulated the Higher Education curriculum, adapting it to new models of student-centred learning (European Commission, 2004, 2009). In this way, this new educational model orients educational programmes and methodologies towards autonomous student learning, in accordance with constructivist principles, promoting the use of teaching and learning strategies and tools beyond learning based merely on the accumulation of knowledge (Geraldo et al., 2010; Iglesias Xamaní, 2013).

Over the past few years, a number of new technological and pedagogical approaches have emerged in classroom learning strategies, ranging from the flipped classroom (Hamdan et al., 2013; Hung et al., 2019; Sergis et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018), to experiential learning (Bontchev et al., 2018; Finch et al., 2015). All of these approaches have shown the potential for integrating technology into the learning process in a wide range of disciplines (Briz-Ponce et al., 2017; Malaquias et al., 2018). In this sense, the use of new technologies in teaching complements traditional methodologies to facilitate the student teaching-learning process. Of all these technologies, the virtual laboratory has become one of the most widely used tools in different fields of education, from biology and chemistry to physics (Achuthan et al., 2018; Brinson, 2017; Dyrberg et al., 2017; Hodges et al., 2018; Hsu, 2020; Nolen & Koretsky, 2018; Špernjak & Šorgo, 2018; Wang et al., 2015; Winkelmann et al., 2020). Several studies have shown that the virtual laboratory is just as effective a learning tool as a traditional hands-on laboratory when it comes to enhancing student understanding and knowledge, irrespective of discipline (Brinson, 2015a; Lindsay & Good, 2005; Sun et al., 2008).

2. Virtual Laboratory (VL)

Virtual laboratories have several advantages: experiments can be set-up quickly; they are fully accessible to students, who can repeat experiments as many times as necessary in order to acquire scientific concepts (Heradio et al., 2016; Hmelo et al., 2000; Renken & Nunez, 2013; Zacharia et al., 2008); they enable the exploration of unobservable phenomena (such as electric current or thermodynamic variables) (Chiu et al., 2015; De Jong et al., 2013); they simplify the information obtained in experiments through simulated models, allowing students to acquire concepts more easily (Pyatt & Sims, 2012; Trundle & Bell, 2010; West & Veenstra, 2012); they are safer since they avoid the use of dangerous products or instruments (Heradio et al., 2016; Špernjak & Šorgo, 2018); and finally, they are an economical alternative in these times of economic crisis (Brinson, 2015a; Magin & Kanapathipillai, 2000).

However, they also have disadvantages, including the following: they do not take experimental errors into account; due to the limitations of the simulated model, experiments are constrained to the simulated parameters and within conditions forced by the simulation itself (Cesari et al., 2006; O'Sullivan, 2004; Špernjak & Šorgo, 2018); students do not acquire practical laboratory skills and do not have access to tactile information that drives the acquisition of conceptual knowledge based on cognitive theories (M Abdulwahed & Nagy, 2011; Barsalou, 2007; Zacharia et al., 2012a); they socialize or collaborate little during virtual experiments (Law et al., 2019; Špernjak & Šorgo, 2009); and virtual labs can lead to a trivializing or irresponsible attitude because students are not required to deal with real experimental environments (Potkonjak et al., 2016).

The development of a virtual laboratory for learning requires understanding of three domains (Koehler & Mishra, 2009): technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge. “Learning by doing” approach derived from the constructivist pedagogy was usually implemented in virtual laboratory environments (Dimitropoulos et al., 2008; Huang et al., 2010; Shih & Yang, 2008; Virvou & Katsionis, 2008). A VL exercise was then a scripted set of experiment procedures intended to be used for teaching purposes and performed by the learner herself. Students have better possibilities to practice real-life situations in the virtual laboratory.

3. Research Laboratory (RL)

Nevertheless, traditional or hands-on laboratories allow students to develop their practical skills in scientific instrumentation, and learn the complexity of science by managing the uncertainties inherent in experiments, through individual or collaborative work (Erdosne Toth et al., 2009; Hofstein & Lunetta, 2003; Špernjak & Šorgo, 2009). For students, the use of instruments and experimental work are more interesting and motivating than the traditional face-to-face classes they passively attend. However, laboratory practical activities must be encompassed within a pedagogical structure in order to enhance critical thinking and reflection in students (Abrahams & Reiss, 2012; Kluge, 2014). Of all the types of laboratories, research laboratories as teaching spaces have received less attention in literature, and any published studies are, at best, incomplete or insufficiently detailed (Feisel & Rosa, 2005; Prins et al., 2009). Research laboratories are facilities for conducting research or investigations into science equipped with advanced instruments and techniques. Well-defined objectives for teaching-learning activities are useful for assessing the adequacy of laboratory activities. The objectives included in the design of laboratory activities can be classified into three

main groups: (1) objectives related to cognition (instrumentation, models, experiment, data analysis and design); (2) objectives involving psychomotor skills (instrument handling and sensory consciousness); and (3) objectives relating to affective domain (motivation, creativity, communication, teamwork and laboratory ethics) (Feisel & Rosa, 2005).

4. Combining Research and Virtual Laboratories

Several studies have focused on using a combination of hands-on and virtual laboratories (Herodotou et al., 2018; Hodges et al., 2018; Jaakkola & Nurmi, 2008; Kapici et al., 2019; Olympiou & Zacharia, 2012). However, the discussion is still open in the literature on how to combine the two types of laboratories, some studies being in favour of performing the activity in hands-on laboratory first and then virtual laboratory, and other studies being just the opposite. On the other hand, several studies concluded that there was no unequivocal evidence that one combination of laboratory environments was better than the other (Chini et al., 2012a; Sullivan et al., 2017). In all these studies, none of hands-on laboratory was a research laboratory, so its use as a teaching space could increase students' interest.

5. Motivation and Attitude toward Scientific Careers

Motivation is an essential cognitive element for successful learning activities. Special attention must be drawn to the important role played by the affective dimensions of learning, such as attitude, interest and self-efficacy (Pintrich & De Groot, 2003). Motivation and learning are very closely connected, i.e. the more interested a student is in a topic, the more inclined he or she will be to learn about that topic (S. Hidi

& Harackiewicz, 2000; Rotgans & Schmidt, 2014; Weibel et al., 2012). Interest may be related to psychological state caused by external factors, or to a situation in which students show a positive and persistent attitude towards a topic. Attitude towards science include anxiety towards science, self-esteem in science, motivation towards science, enjoyment of science, or fear of failure in science (Osborne et al., 2003).

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 6 introduces the research questions. In Section 7, the proposed method was described including a description of the participants, data sources with instruments, data analysis, and the followed procedure. Section 8 presents the experimental results. Finally, conclusions are given in Section 9.

6. Research questions

The authors of this study believe that virtual and research laboratories are not exclusive alternatives. In the current study, we focused on the effects of using a research laboratory, a virtual laboratory, or combined in an integral learning activity, on students' conceptual understanding and interest. As far as we know, this is the first time the proposed blended activity has been used in literature. Therefore, this study was performed to answer the following research questions (RQs):

RQ1: What is the effect of using RL, VL, or RL together with VL on students' understanding about electron microscopy?

RQ2: What is the effect of using RL, VL, or RL together with VL on students' interest?

7. Method

7.1. Participants

The students participating in this study were fourth-year students at Pablo de Olavide University (Spain) during the 2016-2017 and 2017-2018 academic years. The students attended the face-to-face Forensic Physics course on the Criminology degree. The elective course consisted of a 20-week period during the first semester of the academic year. This course introduced students to the forensic applications of physics through the study of several topics. Students studied the physics behind forensic science methods used to gather evidence and reconstruct crime scenes. The course topics included car accident reconstruction (accident dynamics, collision modelling and accident reconstruction and simulation) (1-12 weeks), ballistics (types, configuration and function of firearms, internal and external ballistics, flight dynamics of ammunition, wound ballistics) (12-16 weeks), and advanced forensic techniques (optical and electron microscopy, mass spectrometry) (16-20 weeks) where the proposed activity was carried out. The sample consisted of all 124 students from both academic years, 28.2% of whom were women (N=35) and 71.8% men (N=89) (see Table 1).

<INSERT TABLE 1>

7.2.Data sources

Two quantitative/qualitative tools were used in this study: a questionnaire and a concept test. Both instruments were presented to the students through online and anonymous surveys allowing response through their laptops or mobile phones. The first instrument was an in-house questionnaire, which was used to measure students' interest and attitude during the proposed learning activity. The questionnaire consisted of 9 questions or items using a Likert-type answer formats with 5 possible responses ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree (see Table 2). The questionnaire was adapted from different instruments previously validated to evaluate interest and attitude

(Baldwin et al., 1999; Bandura, 2006; Cortright et al., 2013; Jones et al., 2000; Linnenbrink-Garcia et al., 2010). Items 1 to 4 of the questionnaire reflected students' interest during the proposed activity comparing with practical sessions in teaching laboratories, and their interest towards a professional career. The students' attitude towards the proposed activity was covered from items 5 to 9.

<INSERT TABLE 2>

A test of the questionnaire's reliability was performed using Cronbach's alpha and yielding an acceptable value of .726. However, Cronbach's alpha coefficient could have been affected by number of items and it does not perform well with continuous variables (Dunn et al., 2014). For this reason, McDonald's omega coefficient was calculated (Gerbing & Anderson, 1988; McDonald, 1999), yielding a value of .81, thus confirming reliability of the questionnaire used (Katz, 2011).

The second instrument was a diagnostic or concept test that was administered before (pre-test) and immediately after the proposed activity had been carried out (post-test). The test measured conceptual understanding and identified misconceptions through 10 questions randomly extracted from Appendix A.

7.3.Data analysis

R code version 3.4.3 was used for the quantitative analysis of the results. The statistical techniques started with measures of central tendency and dispersion. The internal consistency of the questionnaire was based on Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's omega. A Shapiro-Wilk test was performed to determine the normality of the pre-test and post-test scores for small samples. Statistical methods based on ANOVA, ANCOVA, and Student test-t were carried out in order to analyse collected data. Finally, effect size was measured using Cohen's d and partial η^2 .

7.4.Procedure

Firstly, the topic began with several face-to-face classes on the physical background and characteristics of advanced techniques used in forensic science including electron microscopy (16-18 week). Immediately afterwards, all students carried out a pre-test containing questions extracted from Appendix A.

Then, three teaching-learning activities were designed combining a research laboratory and a virtual laboratory: a research laboratory (RL), a virtual laboratory (VL), and both (VL+RL) (see Table 1). Those activities were included within advanced forensic techniques topic at the end of the semester (16-20 weeks). Students were randomly divided into three sub-groups to carry out the proposed teaching-learning activities (40, 41 and 43 respectively).

<INSERT FIGURE 1>

In first group (RL), students participated in an activity focusing on the use in forensic science of a Scanning Electron Microscope, Zeiss GeminiSEM 300 model (see Fig.1) during 18-19 weeks. The proposed research laboratory activity consisted of a detailed description of the parts of a scanning electron microscope (electron gun, electron beam, anode, condenser lens, objective lens, sample holder, and electron detector). Then, sample preparation was described briefly. The sample need to have a conductive surface using a gold sputtering system, and a carbon tape may be used to adhesively bond the sample to the holder. Samples were carefully selected for the topic studied, three samples of filaments being taken from car headlights in order for students to differentiate whether headlights during traffic accident were on, off or previously melted (see Fig. 2). Next, sample introduction system into electron microscope chamber

was described showing how to vent, open SEM sample chamber, insert a sample and turn on the pumps to allow system to reach vacuum.

<INSERT FIGURE 2>

Finally, the procedure to capture a SEM image of filaments was shown. Students were observing how to select the operating voltage, use the Auto Focus mode, increase magnification level, and adjust focusing knobs to bring image into focus.

Additionally, students discussed about characteristics that could differentiate each type of filament, and their possible use in an expert appraisal process. Finally, students carried out a post-test identical to previous one in order to check the effect of using RL on students' achievement.

On the other hand, a virtual laboratory was used as a teaching and learning activity (weeks 18-19) for a second group of students (VL). The activity was conducted during class time in a computer classroom. The selected platform was MyScope™ developed by the Australian Microscopy and Microanalysis Research Facility (https://myscope.training/SEM_simulator.html). The online suite comprised a range of e-learning modules for SEM, transmission electron microscopy (TEM), microanalysis, X-ray diffraction (XRD), atomic force microscopy (AFM) and light microscopy (Cribb et al., 2011; Freed et al., 2020; Ringer & Apperley, 2014).

VL experiment was designed to exactly replicate previous RL experiment. The learning environment provided a real world environment for meaningful and authentic knowledge (Jonassen, 1994). VL experiment was a self-directed learning activity that was composed of the aforementioned SEM module. The student was expected to follow a thorough set of step-by-step instructions to accomplish the VL assignment.

<INSERT FIGURE 3>

SEM module focused on three aspects: the description of key SEM components and image formation; basic microscope operations; and manipulation of acquisition parameters (voltage, distance, brightness or contrast) in order to obtain a quality image of a given sample (see Fig. 3-4).

MyScope allow users to explore the SEM and even break it, for example, the filament fails if handled incorrectly. A progress bar on the virtual machines was added helping students avoid frustration. The number of steps were showed allowing a student to assess the approximate time that will be needed to complete the task. Samples have to be inserted into electron microscope through venting, opening door chamber, inserting it and turning on the vacuum pumps. Then, students have to capture a SEM image of the sample selecting the operating voltage, using the Auto Focus mode, increasing magnification level, and finally adjusting focus.

<INSERT FIGURE 4>

Finally, the students performed a post-test containing random questions from Appendix A after completion of the computer classroom activity in order to check the effect of the use of VL on students' achievement.

On the other hand, a third group of students carried out a combination of previous activities in a virtual laboratory (18-19 week) and followed by a research laboratory (VL+RL) (19-20 week), because there are some indications that performing virtual laboratories first increased students' learning (Kapici et al., 2019). VL and RL activities were exactly the same as those described previously.

Finally, all students took end of course exam containing 10 questions randomly selected from those available on the MyScope webpage (see Appendix A) to verify learning process, and they also filled out the questionnaire included in this study. Students only filled in the corresponding items according to the activity they performed (see Table 1).

8. Results

Fig. 5 shows the impact of the different activities on students' knowledge. ANOVA results showed that there were no differences among the groups on the pre-test ($F = 2.227$; $p = 0.112$). Levene's test shows that homogeneity of variance was not significant ($F = 2.153$; $p = 0.121$) and the effect size was small (partial $\eta^2 = 0.035$). Separate paired samples t tests showed that each class increased significantly its score from pre-test to post-test on conceptual test (RL, $t(39) = 3.834$, $p < 0.001$; VL, $t(40) = 4.437$, $p < 0.001$; VLRL, $t(42) = 6.833$, $p < 0.001$), but not from post-test to end of course exam (RL, $t(39) = 1.582$, $p = 0.122$; VL, $t(40) = 0.614$, $p = 0.543$; VLRL, $t(42) = 0.446$, $p = 0.658$). Previously, a Shapiro-Wilk normality test for small samples ($n < 50$) was performed. The assumption check of normality was not significant suggesting that all pairwise differences were normally distributed, and therefore the assumption was not violated.

<INSERT FIGURE 5>

Then, an ANCOVA using pre-test score as covariate indicated that groups differed on their post-test scores ($F = 9.091$; $p < 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.131$). To understand which group's post-test scores were reliably different from the others, post hoc tests were carried

out. Post hoc analysis revealed that post-test scores of the group in which research and virtual laboratories were combined (VL+RL) were higher than for the group that followed only virtual laboratories (VL) ($t=3.619$, $p<0.001$, $d = 0.778$) and only research laboratory (RL) ($t = 3.753$, $p <0.001$, $d = 0.818$). However, VL and RL groups achieved similar post-test scores ($t = 0.124$, $p = 0.992$, $d = 0.03$). All groups significantly improved their conceptual knowledge about the topic of electron microscopy. Furthermore, the overall picture suggested is that using a combination of research and virtual laboratories provides a better learning opportunity than using research or virtual laboratories alone for teaching about electron microscopy, and also that replacing research laboratories with a laboratory that includes virtual components resulted in similar results.

On the other hand, in order to study whether the effect of the proposed activities is maintained over time, the students' grades in the end of course exam have been analysed. Closer examination of the results revealed that the increase in correct answers was not as clear at end of course exam. These results indicated that there a long-term improvement in students' knowledge. A Student t test was carried out for the two related samples (post-test/end course exam) for each group (RL, $t(39) = 1.582$, $p = 0.122$; VL, $t(40) = 0.614$, $p = 0.543$; VLRL, $t(42) = 0.446$, $p = 0.568$), revealing that post-test scores of all group did not differ from those obtained in end of course exam.

Results of items included in the questionnaire regarding students' interest are shown in Table 1 (items 1, 2, 3 and 4). Specifically, all students showed great interest in electronic microscopy technique (item 1). However, VL group showed less interest than RL group ($t = 5.399$, $p<0.001$). It is worthwhile highlighting that most students presented a relatively high level of interest to pursue scientific career (item 4). Once

again, VL group showed much less interest in pursuing a scientific job ($t = 2.934$, $p < 0.001$). On the other hand, RL and VL groups considered, as did VL+RL group, that teaching activity was more interesting than traditional hands-on laboratory sessions ($t = 0.689$, $p = 0.245$; $t = 0.916$, $p = 0.179$; respectively).

Students' attitude towards the activity performed in the research laboratory was measured with items 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9. They got a better understanding of electron microscopy using RL and VL laboratories (items 5 and 6) but showing a statistically significant difference between them ($t = 3.856$, $p < 0.001$). The same opinion was expressed in group VL+RL on the independent use of both laboratories.

Remarkably, students did not show a positive attitude towards teaching activities performed exclusively in RL or VL laboratories (item 7 and 8) (mean=3.3, sd=0.7; mean=2.1, sd=0.9, respectively) towards teaching activities carried out exclusively in a virtual laboratory. However, students expressed a very positive attitude on combining virtual and research laboratories (item 9) and revealing a statistically significant difference with using VL neither RL ($t = 12.324$, $p < .001$; $t = 19.866$, $p < 0.001$, respectively).

9. Discussion

In this study, a combined use of a virtual laboratory and a research laboratory was tested to measure the effects on university students' knowledge, interest, and attitudes. Results showed that a VL+RL activity positively affected students' learning performance, as reported in previous studies (Mahmoud Abdulwahed & Nagy, 2009; Akçayır et al., 2016; Cai et al., 2014; Mione et al., 2013). The results for the conceptual

test showed that students who followed a combination of different laboratory environments (VL+RL) improved their conceptual knowledge more than those in RL or VL groups. These results indicate that using research and virtual laboratory environments should be preferred over using a single laboratory environment. It should be noted that these results are limited to the domain of electron microscopy, and other results are possible depending on the specific domain (Olympiou & Zacharia, 2012; Zacharia et al., 2012b).

After post-test, average correct answers were maintained in end of course exam through the teaching activities carried out, mainly regarding the procedure for sample preparation in SEM microscopy, and the material composition of the lenses in an electron microscope. Several works have been carried out to study the effects of learning strategy interventions on student academic performance (de Boer et al., 2018). In few of these studies it was investigated whether interventions have long-term positive effects. In the current study we addressed this question, as it is extremely important for instruction and intervention purposes. The finding that stability of students' correct answers was achieved after teaching activities ended is compatible with the conclusions of previous works regarding intervention studies (Kasperski et al., 2019). In this sense, it is plausible that ongoing improvements in electron microscopy led to a pattern of success, which contributed to the maintenance of achievements over time.

On the other hand, students' perceived value of the combined activity was high, suggesting that from a motivational standpoint, research laboratories and virtual laboratories can complement traditional teaching laboratories. In other words, the proposed activity was considered to have a statistically significant effect on students'

interest. Since goals and interest are essential factors for motivation (Suzanne Hidi & Ann Renninger, 2006; Schunk & Usher, 2012), and professional interest is fuelled by a positive attitude towards the activities of a specific career, the results obtained suggest that the combined activity fosters positive affective states in students, such as attitudes and interest, towards scientific topics. Exposure to real research laboratories has recently been shown to motivate students towards a scientific career (Budassi & Rafailovich, 2018; Christensen et al., 2014; Linn et al., 2015; Rodrigo-Peiris et al., 2018).

Findings reflect students' generally positive attitude towards proposed teaching sessions on electron microscopy. However, students' attitude towards both laboratory and virtual laboratory classes was low in each case. These results may indicate that the students felt more confident in carrying out the teaching activity by combining research and virtual laboratory activities. For this reason, the proposed activity is presented as a complete teaching solution for advanced instrumental techniques in a non-technical career.

Several previous studies have reported similar findings related to a blended or hybrid approach to laboratory teaching (Brinson, 2015b; Kollöffel & de Jong, 2013; Zacharia et al., 2008, 2012a). In this type of teaching activity, both hands-on laboratory and virtual laboratory modalities are combined in an attempt to exploit the benefit of technical knowledge, and economic benefit and feasibility, respectively. Additionally, sequence of hands-on laboratory and virtual laboratory in the blended procedure seems to make little difference. Some studies have reported slightly higher effectiveness when virtual laboratory activity preceded hands-on laboratory activity (Erdosne Toth et al., 2009), while others have described the opposite effect (Carmichael et al., 2012), or no

significant difference (Chini et al., 2012b). Thus, evidence supporting a combination of hands-on laboratory and virtual laboratory as an effective method of instruction is growing.

Finally, results suggest that students' interest in research laboratory activity has potential to improve students' attitudes towards the use of electron microscopy in Criminology. As non-science students tend to have negative attitudes toward science (Osborne et al., 2003), the inclusion of the proposed activity in Forensic Physics course has been shown to overcome this barrier. Moreover, students acquired greater interest in pursuing a future research career, as stated above, by improving their attitude towards electron microscopy technique. Previous studies have described the way in which several higher-education institutions have incorporated more research-like experiences in a variety of curricula (Jordan et al., 2014; Lopatto, 2007; Shaner et al., 2016; Winkelmann et al., 2015). Evidence exists to suggest that these research-based activities increase interest in science and also in pursuing further research experiences (Tomasik et al., 2013). Therefore, the findings presented here add further evidence to confirm that research experience has a positive impact on students' motivation to pursue research careers in the future. Currently, an alternative to research laboratories is being developed through their transformation into computerised laboratories (Childers & Jones, 2017; Scanlon et al., 2002). Remotely accessed laboratories have emerged as an alternative to hands-on laboratories, but their effectiveness on conducting to science learning may be dependent upon motivation and social factors and how the course implement those new technologies (Corter et al., 2011).

Limitations of this study involve that students can not refer to the instructors or peers for guidance during VL sessions. In the future, it would be a good option to

explore the possibility of conducting VL sessions under collaborative environments. Hence, students can incorporate gestures or voices enhancing the teaching-learning process. Further studies considering the limitations found in this study should be conducted to expand virtual laboratories research.

10. Conclusions

This study consisted in the design and implementation in Criminology of a combine research and virtual laboratory to improve students' conceptual knowledge on electron microscopy. Results suggest that students would benefit from the combined use of virtual and research laboratories to enhance their learning beyond the results that could be obtained using either experience individually, the whole being greater than the sum of its parts. Additionally, assessments performed in this study indicate that students benefited from their participation in this combined activity, increasing interest and positive attitudes towards scientific careers.

In the authors' opinion, hybrid experiences are a potentially powerful tool for obtaining motivational and performance-related benefits. Further research is necessary to continue investigating such aspects of promising hybrid design elements, as including remote access laboratories to replace hands-on laboratories.

Availability of data and materials

All data of this research project is available with the authors and can be made available on requests if required.

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Ethics declarations

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Tables

Table 1. Demographic data of students including academic year, gender, and teaching-learning activity (research laboratory (RL), a virtual laboratory (VL), and both (VL+RL)).

Academic year	Gender	RL		VL		VL+RL	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
2016-2017	Female	5	27.8	4	23.5	7	30.4
	Male	13	72.2	13	76.5	16	69.6
	Total	18	100	17	100	23	100
2017-2018	Female	7	31.8	8	33.3	4	20.0
	Male	16	68.2	16	66.7	16	80.0
	Total	22	100	24	100	20	100
Total		40	32.3	41	33.1	43	34.7

Table 2. Means (and standard deviations) of questionnaire data for RL, VL and VL+RL groups.

	RL	VL	VL+RL
Item 1. The electron microscopy images viewed during class interested me	4.5(5)	3.9(4)	4.4(5)
Item 2. Research laboratory-based sessions are more interesting than teaching laboratories-based practical sessions	4.6(7)	-	4.7(6)
Item 3. Virtual laboratory-based sessions are more interesting than teaching laboratories-based practical sessions	-	4.6(5)	4.5(5)
Item 4. I am interested in the future to devote myself to research in a laboratory	4.1(9)	3.6(6)	4.2(7)
Item 5. I understand electron microscopy better with research laboratory sessions than with face-to-face classes	4.7(7)	-	4.7(6)
Item 6. I understand electron microscopy better with virtual laboratory sessions than with face-to-face classes	-	4.1(7)	4.2(6)
Item 7. Teaching about electron microscopy should be based only on research laboratory sessions	3.3(7)	-	3.2(6)
Item 8. Teaching about electron microscopy should be based only on virtual laboratory sessions	-	2.1(9)	2.3(6)
Item 9. Teaching about electron microscopy should be based on both virtual and research laboratory sessions	-	-	4.7(5)

Figure captions

Fig. 1. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM), Zeiss GeminiSEM 300 model installed in the research laboratory including a brief description of its elements.

Fig. 2. Images obtained by electron microscopy of filaments of car headlights during an accident: (left) on, (center) off, (right) fused.

Fig. 3. SEM components in the VL.

Fig. 4. Virtual laboratory of electron microscopy: sample chamber vent (upper-left corner), sample chamber opening (upper-right corner), sample chamber evacuation (lower-left corner), and SEM image focusing (lower-right corner).

Fig. 5. Average percent of correct answers in pre-test, post-test, and end of course exam for RL, VL and VL+RL groups (only including questions regarding electron microscopy).

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

Fig. 3.

Fig. 4.

Fig. 5.